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Abstract

This deliverable outlines the final discussions on sustainability and exploitation of project's results. This final report includes an overview of pathways to impact emerging from the project activities and how the consortium conveys sustainability actions regarding key concepts such as governance, infrastructure as well as data management and uptake, including cross-cutting security issues. The report also includes the consortium and partners strategies for exploiting results.

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Executive Summary

This report provides an analysis of sustainability and exploitation pathways for the SUBMERSE project, which focuses on developing a standardised scientific instrument utilising active submarine fibre-optic communication cables as environmental sensors. The project's ultimate goal is to enhance ocean, geohazard and environmental monitoring by integrating Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) systems. These technologies are deployed across multiple locations, providing large-scale, open datasets useful for scientific, industrial and public sectors.

Key findings include the project's significant potential to contribute to scientific advancement, environmental sustainability and industrial competitiveness by leveraging existing fibre-optic infrastructure. SUBMERSE is not only pioneering new data handling methodologies but is also fostering interdisciplinary collaboration between academia, industry and public organisations. This contributes to position SUBMERSE as a potential leader in advancing fibre-sensing technologies relevant to geophysics, marine and environmental monitoring.

Building on the project results, the report highlights several pathways to impact emerging from SUBMERSE activities. The analysis shows that the integration of fibre-optic sensing technologies into submarine communication cables has the potential to generate significant scientific, societal, economic and environmental benefits. In particular, the project demonstrates how standardised sensing instruments and interoperable data workflows can strengthen European research infrastructures, enable new forms of ocean and geohazard monitoring and support collaboration between academia, industry and public authorities.

The report also discusses key sustainability considerations necessary to ensure the long-term viability of the project results beyond the lifetime of the grant. Reflections within the consortium emphasise the importance of developing appropriate governance arrangements, securing sustainable infrastructure management and ensuring robust data stewardship. Rather than creating new standalone structures, partners highlight the potential of embedding SUBMERSE outcomes within existing European research infrastructure ecosystems, such as distributed data networks and scientific communities. This approach could support continuity, promote interoperability and strengthen integration with established research and policy frameworks.

Finally, the report outlines the exploitation strategy for the project's key results. Partners identify different pathways for uptake depending on their institutional interests and capabilities, ranging from scientific use and open data services to industrial innovation and technology development. The exploitation approach therefore combines open science principles with targeted opportunities for further technological development and collaboration with industry, aiming to maximise the long-term value and practical application of the project outcomes.

1 Introduction

This report presents the **final sustainability and exploitation analysis** of the SUBMERSE project. It outlines the main exploitation strategies for the core project outputs as well as the project components sustainability pathways. These issues were explored across T4.5 ‘Exploitation, Impact and Sustainability’ including different activities to discuss and analyse among the consortium including consortium meetings, two in-person workshops, policy interviews and complemented with desk research on policy landscape and constructing impact pathways.

This report responds to the question of how to make the pathways to impact sustainable and design exploitation strategies for key project outputs, accelerating the achievement of desired impacts. Based on project discussions, three main focus areas are presented: governance models, infrastructure sustainability and maintenance and data management and uptake by different end-users’ groups.

1.1 About the project

The SUBMERSE project is a response to the call Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools, and methods (HORIZON-INFRA-2022-TECH-01). It aims to improve scientific research by developing an advanced instrument that leverages existing ocean submarine fibre-optic communication cables. Integrating advanced sensing equipment on active cables operated by the National Research and Education Networks (NREN) will enrich the data services offered by organisations like the European Plate Observing System (EPOS-ERIC) and the Copernicus Marine Service by enabling the collection and dissemination of FAIR-compliant Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) data.

At the heart of SUBMERSE is the development of a standardised scientific instrument that integrates both DAS and SOP technologies into a single telecommunications submarine cable system. This system is being deployed in at least three geographically diverse locations – Norway, Greece, and Portugal – also in collaboration with Pan-European and Pan-American institutions, offering long-term, consistent ocean bottom and near-shore monitoring capabilities. The project also focuses on producing large-scale, open, accessible and inter-operable datasets by designing an efficient data acquisition workflow and producing re-usable software. These datasets outputs and accessible, will benefit a broad range of users, including scientific, industrial and public sectors.

Furthermore, SUBMERSE will assess the cost-efficiency of using existing telecommunication systems, thus contributing to the technological advancement of the global telecom industry and creating new market opportunities. The project will also emphasise training and capacity-building activities, enhancing the ability of stakeholders to collect, interpret, and reuse the data generated. By developing a roadmap and strategy for sustainable research infrastructure, SUBMERSE aims to ensure the long-term viability of both the infrastructure and the data it generates, thereby strengthening the European research area and its integration into global innovation systems.

2 Methodological approach

The analysis of sustainability and impact is based on a methodological design that looks to capture different perspectives from consortium partners and a wider network of stakeholders.

The first phase of this task involved collection of information through an online consultation and meetings with key stakeholders at relevant conferences and directly in a dedicated workshop in Potsdam in 2024. The interim report included an analysis of project pathways to impact, the preliminary findings on the sustainability core issues and initial outline of the exploitation strategy. Setting up the scene, the interim report included an analysis of **project impact pathways** (included in annex of this report), looking to identify how different project activities are paving the way to concrete impacts in four areas: scientific, societal, economic and environmental. This was done using the Theory of Change (ToC) approach, defined as a logical description of how and why anticipated changes take place. We looked for causal links that help to reconstruct mechanisms on how SUBMERSE activities and data collected using the infrastructure generates some direct results (i.e., outputs) that can lead to certain short- or long-term effects (i.e. outcomes) and interacting with wider circumstances and influences lead to specific impacts.

Moving on the second phase, the consortium moved into deepening the discussions of sustainability with focus on core emerging topics: governance models, infrastructure long-term plans (after project ends), data handling and uptake by different end-users groups. To this end, the consortium organised a workshop as part of a F2F meeting in Lisbon in 2025, to discuss more concrete pathways of actions for these topics. The work was complemented by a collaborative work online on the exploitation strategies of core project outputs (Key Exploitable Results – KERs) and a series of policy interviews aiming to capture expectations from project related policy areas (research infrastructures, digitalisation policy and marine security). The analysis of results was compared and integrated to the initial discussion, posing open questions to main issues of impact and sustainability and the vision of the consortium around them. The information collected was analysed using content analysis and validated with the consortium.

Figure 1. Impact, sustainability and exploitation methodological design

3 Impact analysis

This section of the report focuses on understanding how all the different activities implemented in the project are embedded in wider policy discussions and how they are contributing to the impact pathways outlined in the interim report. In particular, this section presents an overall understanding of the pathways, including a definition and what it means in the medium and long-term. It also includes reflections emerging from the different workshops and meeting exchanges.

3.1 Policy landscape

3.1.1 Submarine Cables: from security to resilience

Submarine cables carry 99% of global digital data traffic and are exposed to a wide spectrum of risks, including natural hazards such as typhoons, landslides, earthquakes and seafloor currents as well as human activities like fishing and anchoring.¹ The sabotage of the Nord Stream pipelines in October 2022 further highlighted the vulnerability and strategic importance of subsea infrastructure.² In this context, strengthening resilience has become a central objective, referring to the capacity of systems not only to absorb shocks but also to recover rapidly from disruptions and return to operational levels close to normal.³

Within the European Union, undersea cables are increasingly recognised as a strategic vulnerability. However, the policy response remains fragmented and indirect, as no single EU body holds a primary mandate for cable security and resilience. Instead, responsibility is dispersed across five policy domains: maritime security, cyber security, ocean governance, digital and infrastructure policy, and external action including development, security and defence policy.

- **Maritime security:** Undersea cables appear in the EU Maritime Security Strategy and related actions, with roles for agencies like European Maritime Safety Agency (**EMSA**), European Fisheries Control Agency (**EFCA**), and the European Border and Coast Guard Agency, **Frontex**, as well as coast guard cooperation forums. However, cable protection is usually bundled under broader “maritime infrastructure” rather than treated as a distinct priority.
- **Cyber security:** Cables are framed as part of the wider digital and cyber ecosystem. The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (**ENISA**) and EU cyber legislation (e.g. on critical entities and network security) touch on cable-related risks, but there is no dedicated, cable-specific cyber framework—protection is mostly implicit.

¹ Bricheno L., et. al (2024) The diversity, frequency and severity of natural hazard impacts on subsea telecommunications networks, *Earth-Science Reviews*, Volume 259, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2024.104972>

² Robert McCabe et al. (2023) Under the radar: Ireland, maritime security capacity, and the governance of subsea infrastructure, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839.2023.2248001>

³ Omer M, et. Al (2009) Measuring the resilience of the global internet infrastructure system, 3rd Annual IEEE Systems Conference

- Cable issues are scattered across **ocean governance, marine policy, and digital infrastructure** agendas. They intersect with marine protected areas, seabed use, and connectivity initiatives, but without a single lead actor or integrated policy line.
- **External action:** Undersea cable resilience appears in **development cooperation, foreign policy instruments, and EEAS/EDA work**, including hybrid threats and EU–NATO cooperation. Still, cables are usually addressed tangentially, not as a central theme. Also, Brexit adds complexity because of the UK’s key position in cable routes and security cooperation.

In response to these challenges, the EU proposed in 2024 a recommendation on the security and resilience of submarine cable infrastructures. This initiative outlines a set of actions at both national and EU levels aimed at improving submarine cable security and resilience. This action will be implemented through a better coordination across the EU, both in terms of governance and funding.⁴ The recommendation focuses on three core elements:

- **Improving Coordination:** establishing better coordination across the EU to manage and protect submarine cable infrastructures.
- **Enhancing Governance:** strengthening governance structures to ensure the security and resilience of these critical assets.
- **Increasing Funding:** allocating appropriate funding to support the necessary measures to safeguard submarine cable systems.

Building on this foundation, the EU Action Plan on Cable Security, presented on 9 February 2025 during the Baltic Energy Independence Day in Vilnius, sets out a new approach. It identified four strategic priorities to secure the EU critical network infrastructure: prevention, detection, response, repair and deterrence. This action plan designs a clear approach, based on these four priorities, to further increase the resilience and security of submarine cables, covering both communication and electricity cable infrastructure (EU Action plan on Cable Security, 2025)⁵.

A central aspect of resilience is the need to **increase investment in submarine cable infrastructure**. This includes enhancing redundancy, strengthening security capabilities and improving repair capacities. The EU also recognises the importance of reducing dependencies on non-EU actors, particularly in markets where certain vendors are considered high-risk. To address this, the Commission plans to propose an EU Investment Framework for cable infrastructures for the Union’s resilience and security.

The next implementation steps involve the progressive rollout of specific measures in 2025 and 2026 in cooperation with Member States and ENISA. Planned actions include mapping existing and planned submarine cable infrastructures, conducting a coordinated risk assessment, developing a Cable Security Toolbox of mitigation measures, and establishing a priority list of Cable Projects of European or European Interest⁶.

Moreover, these systems can function as large-scale geographical sensor networks capable of monitoring surrounding activities, anticipating threats, and acting as early warning systems to protect both cable infrastructure and nearby environments. Their potential spans civilian applications, such as environmental monitoring, and military purposes (EU Action plan on Cable Security, 2025).

The promotion of smart cables is reflected in the CEF Digital 2024–2027 work programme, as well as in the Recommendation on Secure and Resilient Submarine Cable Infrastructures, which highlights the role of sensor and monitoring technologies and the deployment of innovative solutions to detect and deter threats. Feasibility

⁴ [Recommendation on the security and resilience of submarine cable infrastructures | Shaping Europe’s digital future](#)

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025JC0009>

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/cipr/items/884566/en>

studies will be launched under the CEF in coordination with the European Defence Fund and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF). Existing Blue Invest projects already contribute to underwater observation, detection, communication and surveillance technologies, including launch and docking solutions for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) and swarm intelligence systems. Coordination will also be ensured with Horizon Europe, notably through dedicated actions aimed at advancing the state of the art in submarine cable infrastructure.

3.1.2 Research infrastructure outlook

In September 2025, the European Commission launched a new European strategy on research and technology infrastructures⁷ aimed at reinforcing Europe's global leadership while **making infrastructures more integrated, accessible and resilient**. The strategy emphasises increasing capacities, mobilising investment aligning facilities with user needs and maximising the potential of digitalisation and artificial intelligence. It also seeks to simplify access for researchers and innovative companies, cultivate talent in Europe through strong career pathways in research and technology infrastructures and enhance the international dimension and resilience, particularly regarding access to critical data and facilities.

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)⁸ landscape includes several Environmental Landmarks directly relevant to marine and solid Earth observation, such as EPOS ERIC, EMSO ERIC, and Euro-Argo ERIC, alongside other infrastructures addressing atmospheric, ecological and environmental domains. Marine RIs are diverse, spanning from fixed observatories and data centres to research vessels and autonomous vehicles. Within the environmental domain, initiatives like the European environmental research infrastructures (ENVRI) functions as a dynamic forum, enabling infrastructures at different stages of maturity to exchange good practices and promote innovation.

Despite their strategic importance, research infrastructure ecosystems face persistent challenges. ESFRI analyses highlight the need to modernise ageing observation networks, improve coordination between infrastructures and across domains, strengthen skills in data science and modelling and enhance the integration of heterogeneous data sources. Digitalisation is transforming research infrastructures through advanced computing networks and software capabilities, supported by initiatives such as EuroHPC and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). However, limited interoperability between major digital initiatives constrains their full potential, underscoring the **need for harmonised standards and coordinated governance**.

OECD analysis⁹ further conceptualises research infrastructure ecosystems as meta-structures operating beyond individual governance models. A major challenge is ensuring their long-term sustainability, as dedicated organisational models and stable resourcing mechanisms are often lacking. While there is a clear trend toward facilitating access through common portals and promoting FAIR data principles, heterogeneity in data policies, licensing regimes and national regulations complicates harmonisation efforts. Balancing open access with intellectual property considerations, addressing cybersecurity risks and exploring the use of artificial intelligence for managing large and heterogeneous datasets are emerging priorities, though **standardised ecosystem-level** guidelines remain under development.

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_2097

⁸ https://landscape2024.esfri.eu/media/w24ifqps/esfri-la-2024_section1.pdf

⁹ OECD (2025), "Fostering research infrastructure ecosystems for addressing complex scientific and societal challenges", *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers*, No. 183, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/34797721-en>.

3.1.3 Data policy landscape: open for wider uptake

Over the past two decades, both oceanographic and seismic data management have undergone a significant transformation, moving from institutionally confined datasets toward more **open, interoperable and distributed systems of access**. In the early 2000s, oceanographic data were largely stored within individual research institutions, with limited standardisation and few mechanisms for sharing. The progressive development of repositories and interoperability tools, including platforms such as SeaDataNet, PANGAEA, DataOne, and EMODnet, has substantially improved accessibility. However, despite these advances, ocean data remain highly fragmented, and researchers often face difficulties in locating, accessing and integrating datasets. Inconsistent metadata protocols and the absence of harmonised data management structures continue to complicate cross-disciplinary and geographically broad analyses.¹⁰

At the European level, the Union has invested in major data infrastructures to facilitate access to quality-controlled marine observation data and to support long-term knowledge integration. Core services such as the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS), the Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) provide global and pan-European data, forecasts, analysis, and projections. These platforms support open access models and interoperability while ensuring system integrity through secure authentication mechanisms. Copernicus Marine data, in particular, are fully open and free to access with only a citation requirement, while security measures focus on protecting infrastructure through secure login procedures and network configuration options rather than restricting data use. Efforts to integrate and operationalise these large data resources are further reflected in initiatives such as the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO), which aims to make ocean knowledge more accessible to citizens, scientists, entrepreneurs and policymakers through interactive visualisation and modelling tools.

In seismology, similar principles of distributed data management and coordinated access apply. ORFEUS¹¹, which operates the waveform pillar of the Thematic Core Services in Seismology within EPOS-ERIC, coordinates the infrastructure for seismic waveform data and station metadata through the European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA), a distributed federation of data centres that collect and securely archive data gathered by European research infrastructures. These centres store data from broadband sensors, accelerometers, infrasound sensors and other geophysical instruments. Even though EIDA consists of multiple data centres with distinct data holdings, they share a common API for access and use standard formats for both data and metadata. Therefore, through the use of routing services and smart clients, the user does not even need to be aware of which data centre hold which piece of data. An additional layer of integration is provided by the interdisciplinary EPOS Data Portal¹², which enables transparent access for the wider geoscience research community.

Within this broader landscape of distributed and interoperable data management, specific **data policy frameworks** of Research Infrastructures such as those of EPOS and EMSO-ERIC provide structured approaches to governance, access and long-term stewardship, ensuring that data are handled in ways that support open science while maintaining quality, traceability, and security.

The EPOS Data Policy¹³ establishes a comprehensive framework for the management, sharing, and preservation of solid Earth science data across a distributed European research infrastructure. It is structured around a lifecycle approach that includes three main phases: data provision, data integration and data access and reuse. A key feature of the EPOS Data Policy is its strong alignment with international frameworks and European

¹⁰ Haimson M. et al., 2025, An overview of the ocean data ecosystem, European Geosciences Union
<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-21-3131-2025>

¹¹ <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/>

¹² <https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org/>

¹³ <https://www.epos-eu.org/documents/epos-data-policy-dec-2025>

legislation relevant to data governance, interoperability, and security. It explicitly references FAIR principles, OECD recommendations, GEO principles, TRUST and CARE, and integrates a wide range of EU legal instruments (e.g. INSPIRE Directive and the Database and Software Directives).

The EMSO ERIC Data Policy¹⁴ provides a complementary framework for managing oceanographic data collected across its distributed network of seafloor and water-column observatories. A unified data policy is therefore essential to ensure consistency while accommodating the diversity of operational models and user needs. The policy is designed to ensure that data are open, high-quality, FAIR-aligned, and responsibly managed, while maintaining flexibility to support diverse analytical approaches and research perspectives. The EMSO ERIC policy is also strongly anchored in the European legal environment. Through this alignment, the policy supports open science while ensuring that data governance remains consistent with broader European frameworks on data access, reuse and protection.

In the international landscape, the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030)¹⁵ plays an important role. In the document “Advancing Ocean Data Sharing for Sustainable Development in areas within national jurisdiction”¹⁶, it identifies in advancing ocean data sharing a fragmented regulatory and governance landscape that shapes how data can be accessed and reused. Different countries apply distinct rules, permissions, and licensing frameworks for data collected within their territorial waters and Exclusive Economic Zones, which can create barriers for private-sector actors willing to share the information they produce. As a result, only a limited portion of ocean data collected through activities such as offshore energy exploration, marine infrastructure development, fisheries and telecommunications is made publicly available, despite its high potential value for science and policy.

These constraints are often linked to issues of data ownership, commercial sensitivity, and the absence of harmonised national policies. The diversity of legal and administrative approaches across jurisdictions makes it difficult to establish consistent practices for sharing data, particularly when datasets are generated by private companies operating under specific contractual or regulatory obligations. This situation contributes to a persistent gap between the volume of data collected and the volume of data that can be accessed and reused for broader societal benefit.

3.2 Pathways to impact

- **SCIENTIFIC DOMAIN: Supporting innovation from basic and applied research through development of high-tech standardised research instruments.**

This pathway investigates how Research Infrastructures (RIs) **standardised technologies could unlock scientific advancement and innovation** in various fields. Within SUBMERSE project, the State of Polarisation (SOP) and Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS) systems are designed to enhance the precision, accuracy, and reliability of data collection and analysis across various research domains (seismology, oceanography, marine ecology, etc.). By standardising fibre-sensing instruments, SUBMERSE is catalysing innovation, thus sharing common approaches, methodologies and access, which ultimately means providing ground for competitive basic and applied research.

For instance, at the end of October 2023, a DAS interrogator was installed at the EMACOM Cable Landing Station in Praia Formosa, in Madeira Island, Portugal, connecting to the Geolab fibre. The position of the cable along the seabed made it possible to not only record P and S waves from local earthquakes but also very clearly record

¹⁴ EMSO data policy (2023) https://emso.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/EMSO_ERIC_Data_Policy_.pdf

¹⁵ <https://oceandecade.org/vision-mission/>

¹⁶ <https://oceandecade.org/pdfviewer/advancing-ocean-data-sharing-for-sustainable-development-in-areas-within-national-jurisdiction/>

acoustic signals that propagated through the SOFAR channel in the water column, the T waves, which are thought to be excited by coupling of elastic waves at significant seafloor topography. The Geolab recordings represent a first observations of T waves close to the source and conversion points, allowing the definitive identification of a group of seamounts between the earthquake and the cable as the origin point of the T waves (Loureiro et. al., 2026)¹⁷. Apart from shedding light on the tectonically active structure and thus improving our knowledge of the earthquake hazard, a fast analysis of the signals from the cable might provide early warning for tsunamis (e.g. Xiao et al. 2024)¹⁸, or in some localities, early warning of strong shaking. Similarly, following the deployment of the DAS in Preveza in early 2025 and in Crotona on the same cable in early 2026, it is now possible to actively monitor the Kefalonia transfer fault from the sea for the first time. Earthquakes along this highly seismically active region off the coast of Greece were difficult to locate due to the poor azimuthal coverage possible with land-based monitoring networks, making monitoring of the potential high-risk zones along the fault line more difficult for earthquake monitoring agencies and for scientists interested in the seismotectonic of the region. These example showcases not only the potential of this technology innovation in scientific terms – moving beyond the state of the art of collecting data for earthquakes and tsunamis but highlights a clear contribution of science to address societal challenges, here the danger from natural hazards, i.e. Tsunamis, earthquakes and submarine volcanoes.

In the short term, the planned provision of standard analysis tools in SUBMERSE will enable researchers to quickly generate new observations from the data collected. This will allow researchers to produce comparable and consistent results, which helps advancing scientific knowledge. In the medium-term, these data collected through the submarine cables are expected to be widely adopted within the scientific community, contributing to the growth of a robust research infrastructure. This infrastructure will support the continuous development of new technologies and methodologies, driving innovation in both fundamental research and practical applications. In the long-term, the widespread use of these standardised tools will facilitate more complex and interdisciplinary research, leading to breakthroughs that address critical environmental and societal challenges, and ultimately, contributing to the long-term impact of sustainable marine and land management.

Connection to Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. Creating high-quality new knowledge: Horizon Europe generates world-class science and creates and diffuses high-quality new knowledge. The implementation of standardised SOP (State of Polarisation) and DAS (Distributed Acoustic Sensing) systems will facilitate the generation of high-quality, consistent, and comparable research data across different domains.
2. Strengthening human capital in Research and Innovation (R&I): Horizon Europe strengthens human capital engaged in R&I. The project will enhance the skills and capabilities of researchers by providing access to advanced, standardised research tools and methodologies, as well as offering training in the effective use of these. This will improve their ability to conduct cutting-edge research, collaborate across disciplines, and achieve reliable results.
3. Fostering the diffusion of knowledge and Open Science: Open Science helps to develop a stronger system for science by giving Europe a competitive advantage through open knowledge. By enabling better and faster access to submarine data through fibre sensing techniques, SUBMERSE will enhance Europe's competitive advantage in science and innovation.

¹⁷ Loureiro, A., Schlaphorst, D., Matias, L., Pereira, A., Corela, C., Gonçalves, S., & Caldeira, R. (2025). First DAS observations from the GeoLab fibre in Madeira, Portugal. *Seismica*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.26443/seismica.v4i2.1482>

¹⁸ Xiao, H., Spica, Z. J., Li, J., Zhan, Z. (2024): Detection of Earthquake Infragravity and Tsunami Waves With Underwater Distributed Acoustic Sensing. - *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51, 2, e2023GL106767. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL106767>

- **SOCIETAL DOMAIN: Enhanced knowledge sharing between academia, industry and general public and awareness raising on socio-environmental issues.**

This pathway looks into the way **RIs can facilitate knowledge sharing** between key stakeholders such as research communities, industries and also broader public, leading to an **increased awareness of social and environmental issues**. By creating platforms and intersectoral networks (e.g. fibre sensing communities, etc.), the project promotes the exchange of ideas and research findings in various fields, also triggering different uptakes of research results. It also refers to the process of enhanced interdisciplinary and applied research in disciplines such as oceanography, biology, chemistry, or engineering.

An example of this pathway is the potential contribution of the data collected and curated through the fibre-sensing technology that could deliver critical real-time information on an ongoing earthquake rupture to national Tsunami warning systems. An important advance in this respect was the development of a plugin that allowed to stream data through the seedlink protocol, which allows integration into standard workflows (see economic domain).

The infrastructure and new science built upon it address some of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- SDG9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) is supported by building the proof of concept for resilient detection systems based on submarine cable infrastructure.
- SDG11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) through the support of disaster risk reduction via integration of real time data feeds with earthquake monitoring agencies, as well as promoting sustainable cities and human settlements through cable protection monitoring and ensuring resiliency of critical infrastructure.
- SDG12 (Responsible consumption and production) is supported through proving the possibility of re-use of existing abandoned submarine telecommunications cables, as well as use of and coexistence with live telecommunications cables.
- SDG13 (Climate Action) is supported by adding data sets to foster the protection, conservation and responsible use of our marine resources.
- SDG14 (Life Below Water) by providing seabed data with relevance to marine life, with relevance and effects to climate change and interestingly also of human activity close to the ocean floor.
- SDG17 (Partnerships for the goals) via integration pathways between existing European research infrastructures and their members, which allows for the development of new technologies, scientific discoveries, multi-stakeholder partnerships and capacity development.

In the medium-term, the pathways are expected to result in a deeper understanding of socio-environmental issues across different sectors of society. In the long-term, this enhanced knowledge-sharing process could contribute to aligning societal, industrial, and academic efforts toward addressing societal challenges (e.g. earthquake and tsunami early detection and warning, etc.).

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions: pursuing clearly defined targets and delivering solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world. SUBMERSE addresses critical socio-environmental challenges by creating platforms for knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary collaboration in diverse fields (oceanography, seismology, etc.) connected to two key EU missions: Oceans and Waters and Climate Change.
2. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society: it is expected that this will increase the relevance of science and innovation in society, while stimulating the societal uptake and deployment of innovative solutions and leveraging business investment.

- **ECONOMIC DOMAIN: Enhanced competitiveness of European industry through co-development with industrial actors of advanced technologies and tools.**

This pathway explores the impact on European competitiveness from joint development of technologies and tools with the private sector. This collaborative approach ensures that the generated innovations are not only cutting-edge but also market-ready, meeting the specific needs and demands for both applied research and industry. By integrating industry expertise and real-world application requirements into research and development process, SUBMERSE puts together industrial and scientific capabilities to create breakthrough innovation.

The core innovation of the project emerges from the close collaboration between scientific institutions and industrial partners to prototype, validate, and deploy fibre-sensing technologies within operational telecommunications infrastructures. By embedding sensing capabilities directly into commercial submarine cable systems, SUBMERSE demonstrates how research-driven innovation can evolve into scalable industrial solutions. The integration of the EllaLink cable as a dual-use scientific and commercial infrastructure illustrates a new model of co-development, where industry requirements for reliability, interoperability, and operational continuity are addressed alongside scientific objectives. Industrial partners such as CORIANT/NOKIA and Alcatel Submarine Networks contribute technological expertise, system integration capabilities and market-oriented perspectives that ensure the developed solutions align with future product portfolios and service opportunities. From an industrial standpoint, optical sensing represents a strategic development pathway, enabling native network monitoring, infrastructure resilience, and new value-added services such as civil protection and environmental monitoring. The collaboration also generates tangible technological assets, including validated sensing deployments, standardised data workflows and open technical documentation that support future commercialization and adoption across European optical networks. The initial dataset retrieved in Madeira exemplifies this shared innovation process: the OptoDAS equipment, acquired by the Government of Madeira from Alcatel Submarine Networks, uses a fibre from the EllaLink cable to measure and record seismic and marine data, demonstrating how jointly developed technologies can transition from experimental deployment to operational capability with societal and economic value.

Another example is the successful cooperation between industrial project partner ASN and academic project partner GFZ in enabling streaming selected channels directly to earthquake observatories and seismological data centres. The standard protocol for this is seedlink¹⁹, originally developed by GFZ, by which time series are streamed in miniseed format with low latency. Another advantage of this protocol is that in case of transmission gaps, those gaps are filled from a copy of the data stored locally, while prioritising the most recent data. The cooperation has resulted in the development of a plugin²⁰ that converts streaming by the ZeroMQ protocol as implemented in the ASN firmware into seedlink and thus allowed seismological data centres to ingest these data without needing to install any additional software beyond the plugin, as well as for earthquake observatories to include them in their workflows. In updated versions of the firmware, ASN now allows preprocessing such as spatial integration and F-K filtering, that use multiple channels to suppress noise in streamed channels and make them more similar to classic seismological data. This development has also spurred other companies to add seedlink streaming capability to their interrogators.

Participation in SUBMERSE allows industry partners to benchmark emerging technologies in real operational environments, advance technology readiness levels, and refine data processing, storage, and interoperability standards based on scientific user requirements. Alcatel Submarine Network representative explained: *“Participation in SUBMERSE has enabled our company to interact closely with data end-users and understand application scenarios. The real-world applications considered in the project has helped us to define and develop support for scientific applications in our technology.”* Meanwhile, CORIANT/NOKIA highlights the project *“offers*

¹⁹ <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/seedlink/en/latest/protocol.html>

²⁰ <https://github.com/SeisComp/seedlink>

the opportunity to test and benchmark our technology alongside research partners and stakeholders in a non-commercial framework. This is invaluable for advancing the TRL of our R&D efforts. Additionally, it allows us to explore scientific pursuits that are lateral to our core R&D activities, providing a platform for early technology rollouts and demonstrations.”

In the medium-term, the adoption of joint industry-academia developments will drive economic growth by opening new markets and enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of existing operations. The successful application of new technologies in different fields will reinforce the position of European companies as leaders in environmental technologies on the global stage. In the long-term, this pathway could contribute to the creation of a dynamic and innovative industrial ecosystem in Europe, capable of responding to emerging challenges and maintaining competitiveness in an evolving market landscape.

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. Generating innovation-based growth: to maintain and improve its relative competitiveness in the global economy, the EU needs a constant supply of new technological output and intellectual property. By integrating industry expertise into research and development process, SUBMERSE ensures that the technologies and tools developed are aligned with market needs and have strong commercial potential.
2. Leveraging investments in R&I: Horizon Europe is expected to play a role as a catalyst for R&D activities within industry, research and academia. SUBMERSE acts as a catalyst for further research, triggering not only quality research but also developing innovation in monitoring processes (e.g. disaster risk reduction).

- **ENVIRONMENTAL DOMAIN: Increased understanding of natural ecosystems leading towards resilient and sustainable marine and land environments.**

This pathway explores the potential of SUBMERSE technological developments to improve the understanding of natural ecosystems, that is key to addressing pressing environmental challenges. By conducting comprehensive and interdisciplinary research, the project aims to uncover the complex interactions and processes that govern ecosystem health and stability. The insights gained from applied research could serve as a foundation for informed decision-making aimed at preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services.

For instance, changes in the seabed can result from various factors, including ocean currents, marine organisms, and maritime activity. Some seabed changes are so subtle that they cannot be detected through conventional research methods. Technologies that employ in-line strain detection, like Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), provide the capability to monitor even the tiniest shifts in the seabed. Developments of SUBMERSE allow the automated detection of baleen whales through recordings of their soundings, as demonstrated with the analysis of continuous data from Madeira. A recent exciting advance demonstrates the possibility to detect whales from the disturbance of the cable by induced currents²¹. Furthermore, long term filtering of DAS records from the Geolab site in Madeira showed that the DAS can serve as a temperature sensor, allowing tracking of water masses at different temperatures. With this tool the processes such as internal tides and mesoscale eddy diffusion can be visualised and analysed.

Awareness creation was done through training modules and courses delivered collocated with conferences. Through training courses, six scientific presentations and a joint booth with partner initiatives Geo-INQUIRE, EMSO ERIC, and EPOS, our team highlighted the growing role of fibre sensing in Earth sciences and how SUBMERSE is advancing this field across Europe at the IAGA–IASPEI Joint Scientific Meeting 2025. Training

²¹ Rørstadbotnen, Robin Andre and Landrø, Martin, Detecting Silent Whales Using Seabed Fibre Optic Cables (December 23, 2025). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=6171939> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.6171939>

courses and modules were also made available through LifeWatch ERIC website and they are made available on the project website. A collaboration with Blue-Cloud will enable to set up a V-Lab allowing to further disseminate the trainings with wider communities. Finally, a community event is planned to take place during the final event, allowing researchers to access ad-hoc trainings on the use cases topics (seismology and oceanography) facilitated by experts from the project and invited recognised speakers.

In the medium-term, the body of knowledge generated will enable more precise and adaptive management of natural resources, ensuring that ecosystems can sustain their vital functions in the face of ongoing environmental changes. The project's findings will inform further multi-disciplinary understanding of our planet and its processes. In the long-term, these efforts will contribute to sustainability of marine and terrestrial environments, creating better ecological networks, capable of withstanding and recovering from disturbances, thus increasing resilience.

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions: pursuing clearly defined targets and delivering solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world. Through comprehensive research, the project provides valuable insights into natural ecosystem dynamics, which are essential for informed decision-making and effective management.

4 Sustainability topics and perspectives

The sustainability reflections emerge from the two rounds of discussion within the SUBMERSE project, moving from exploratory considerations in the initial consultation to more structured, though still evolving, propositions in the subsequent co-creation processes. The synthesis below integrates the principal reflections from the first round and expands them through the operational, strategic and organisational insights generated in the second round of exchanges. The analysis is organised across three interdependent domains: governance, infrastructure, and data.

4.1 Governance

Early reflections on governance were framed by uncertainty regarding long-term stewardship responsibilities, ownership arrangements and the institutional positioning of the project outputs. Partners emphasised that sustainability would depend heavily on the establishment of **clear governance structures** capable of ensuring operational continuity, securing funding and managing stakeholder relationships, particularly where submarine cable infrastructures intersect with national security and critical infrastructure domains.

The first round of discussions underscored governance as both an enabler and a potential barrier. Effective communication channels, clearly articulated security policies and strong coordination with national authorities were identified as prerequisites for long-term viability. At the same time, fragmented national frameworks, limited engagement from security agencies and the complexity of multi-jurisdictional cable systems were recognised as structural challenges that could inhibit continuity. These initial reflections positioned governance less as a fixed institutional design and more as an evolving ecosystem of relationships spanning research infrastructures, public authorities and private cable operators.

The second round of discussions deepened this perspective by differentiating governance across two interconnected layers: governance of the physical infrastructure and governance of the data it produces. This distinction reflects the hybrid nature of SUBMERSE as both a technical deployment and a scientific data infrastructure. Participants converged on the idea that sustainability does not necessarily require the creation of a new standalone entity; rather, it may be more resilient to embed SUBMERSE functions within existing organisational frameworks. Established European research infrastructures and networks — including GÉANT, EPOS-ERIC, EMSO ERIC, and fibre sensing communities — were identified as potential institutional hosts or partners capable of absorbing governance functions.

In this direction, governance sustainability turns to move into **integration strategies** while keeping a **distributed partnership model**. The possibility of creating thematic services within existing RI structures and/or aligning with working groups focused on fibre sensing and seafloor monitoring, was seen as a pragmatic pathway to institutionalise the project. Such integration could also enhance legitimacy, visibility and access to diversified funding streams beyond project-based financing.

However, some open issues remain. For instance, how to formalise commitments among partners in the absence of continued grant funding. Proposed instruments such as Memorandum of Understanding, community charters or national stakeholder councils signal possible approaches, yet their legal weight and operationalisation remain under discussion. Another important dimension concerns private-sector engagement. Cable owners and

operators are essential actors, yet their incentives to participate in long-term governance frameworks are not fully defined. The articulation of a compelling value proposition — balancing infrastructure protection, scientific advancement and potential commercial services — is therefore central to governance sustainability.

4.2 Infrastructure

Infrastructure sustainability emerged as a key sustainability domain related to cost uncertainty, technological obsolescence and ambiguous ownership arrangements. These uncertainties extend to legal obligations, particularly where infrastructure may fall under critical infrastructure protection frameworks such as NIS2²². Initial reflections also highlighted depreciation cycles, storage costs and the need for neutral operational entities capable of managing infrastructure access and ensuring equitable scientific use.

Subsequent discussions significantly expanded the infrastructural analysis by disaggregating sustainability challenges across three layers: cable infrastructure, sensing instruments and operational hosting environments.

With respect to cable infrastructure, sustainability is shaped by the operational realities of global telecommunications systems. Cable lifespans average approximately twenty-five years, yet scientific monitoring technologies evolve on far shorter cycles. This temporal mismatch introduces planning complexity: infrastructures designed for decades of service must accommodate sensing technologies that may change every six to seven years. Although, this is not a major issue as for many methodological advances it is sufficient to exchange interrogating units in the shore stations, and even monitoring with 'obsolete' technology provides highly useful data. Furthermore, DAS technology is also maturing, so technological advances are likely to be more incremental in the future.

The discussions explored the scientific reuse of decommissioned cables as a cost-effective sustainability pathway, though this raises questions around repair liabilities or power provision. The possibility of using alternative bands for DAS interrogation on active (lit) fibres was tested and found to be safe and without any impact on the data transmission. Therefore, scientific sensing without disrupting commercial traffic is technically possible with the appropriate interrogation equipment. However, the experience in SUBMERSE shows that cable operators are generally reluctant to permit such shared use of fibres without comparable benchmark testing to ensure safety of equipment, but also due to the impact on existing cable operator business models where in the case of limited fibres on a cable system, each un-used fibre is a premium valued asset and each usable piece of spectrum comes also at a premium. Because of remaining technical, non-zero risk factors of interference to equipment or cable damage, the preferred default sharing model for industry seems to be to reserve a fibre pair for scientific use in otherwise commercial cables. Thus, the project has built a strong reputation with telecom cable operators, such that we have been able to overcome the reluctance and in turn project participants are sought to offer advice on integrating such technologies into new and existing cable systems.

Other fibre sensing technology like SOP can be inherently compatible with telecom traffic, but unintended consequences of installing additional equipment in landing stations must be carefully considered, if the scientific and NREN community is to continue building the trust of cable operators. During the project timespan there have been instances where field deployments in other cable systems and from other non-SUBMERSE project groups have resulted in potential damage to repeater systems, which are one of the costliest pieces of equipment on a cable system. Due to that heightened industry awareness, Alcatel Submarine Networks were able to provide a warranty preservation assurance for the DAS when utilised on their own cable systems, including the EllaLink cable system. This assures cable operators that the DAS technology deployed during the project is safe to deploy. While the assurance is limited to DAS, it does give a pathway for future trust building with wider industry partners, so as to ensure the sustainability of fibre sensing deployments.

²² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

Such arrangements would require early regulatory engagement and partnership with national research and education networks, as well as negotiated access rights embedded in cable landing permits. These reflections point to sustainability being influenced as much by regulatory diplomacy as by engineering feasibility.

Instrument sustainability presents a different challenge. Monitoring technologies (DAS or SOP systems) evolve rapidly, often not at same rhythm of the infrastructures they monitor. Component obsolescence or calibration requirements further complicate long-term maintenance. Equipment lifetimes of under a decade imply recurring capital investment cycles, necessitating either successive research projects or dedicated national funding lines. Operational hosting adds a further cost layer: fibre leasing, power supply, rack space rental, bandwidth for data transfer and software support all generate recurring expenditures. Without defined ownership or budget allocation, infrastructure risks gradual degradation — a concern explicitly recognised in discussions.

Risk analysis in the second workshop also broadened the sustainability lens. Technical failures (e.g., cable rupture, DAS malfunction), data loss risks, software incompatibilities and travel constraints for specialised maintenance personnel all underscore the need for structured maintenance planning and contingency funding. Of the challenges to sustainability which were discussed, long term sustainability and clarification of operational ownership for data storage infrastructure in each country was highlighted. As such, to keep a track of ongoing discussions, a sustainability catalogue was created for the project, to list all components, ownership considerations, component operator, status post project and business model description. For security purposes, the catalogue is not included in this report.

4.3 Data

Data sustainability was recognised from the outset as both a strategic asset and an operational burden. The first round of reflections emphasised the scientific value of high-quality DAS and SOP datasets, their cross-disciplinary applications and their societal relevance for early warning systems, oceanographic modelling and infrastructure protection (See impact analysis section). Long-term availability and accessibility of such data were seen as central to sustaining project impact.

However, storage costs and data volume quickly emerged as limiting factors. The consortium discussions highlighted funding constraints associated with large-scale data retention and the need to balance quality preservation with financial feasibility. Moreover, responsibilities for data handling — particularly in international waters — were also flagged as governance and legal grey areas requiring coordination with national authorities and cable stakeholders.

The second workshop and further consortium discussions introduced a more operational philosophy of data sustainability, centred on selective retention and value extraction. Rather than indefinite storage, participants proposed prioritising data processing, enrichment and reduction. Raw data would be retained only for defined buffering periods, with automated systems identifying scientifically significant segments for long-term preservation. This approach aligns sustainability with data curation intelligence rather than storage expansion (see Data Management Plan and Data Policy deliverable).

Long-term archiving of representative raw datasets was nonetheless considered essential, particularly to support machine learning development and retrospective analysis. This introduces technical questions around sampling strategies and metadata standards. In this domain, standardisation emerged as a critical enabler. The transition towards homogeneous data formats, interoperable schemas (e.g., JSON) and FAIR-aligned dissemination frameworks was recognised as necessary to broaden scientific uptake. Yet partners acknowledged that establishing such standards can take several years — often exceeding project lifetimes — thereby positioning SUBMERSE as an initiator rather than a completer of standardisation processes.

As sustainability pathway, **established repositories and data centres** linked to European research infrastructures could provide resilient long-term environments, whereas national raw data storage requires dedicated funding agreements. This bifurcation creates a layered sustainability model: stable public repositories for curated outputs, coupled with national buffering systems. Collaboration with European Commission facilitated data collections such as the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) could facilitate data uptake and use, as collected data available for research adhere to FAIR principles. Ingestion of data from the SUBMERSE project into EMODnet is achieved via integration with the Copernicus Marine Service, through which marine data collected in SUBMERSE is published. EMODnet relies on a broad user community, including the Blue Economy, national authorities and administrators, research and academia, non-governmental organisations and citizen science initiatives.

Spatially down-sampled strain rate time series are streamed from all SUBMERSE cables to EIDA, the European Integrated Data Archive (see detailed report in Deliverable D3.2). Metadata are immediately available for these datasets, while the actual datasets are often under rolling embargos, but a substantial tranche of data from the Geolab cable are already accessible, and further data will follow. Once archived at EIDA nodes, the data are accessible through the EPOS-ERIC portal. Continued data storage at EIDA nodes is ensured beyond the end of the SUBMERSE project.

Data uptake and use were also central themes. Data sustainability is inseparable from active utilisation. Ensuring high-quality, gap-free datasets and accessible analytical tools were all identified as key actions to enable adoption. Nonetheless, tensions persist between openness and sensitivity. Security classifications, geopolitical considerations and commercial confidentiality may restrict data release. Where dissemination is not possible, deletion policies were proposed, raising further questions about lost scientific opportunity.

5 Exploitation strategy

Based on the data analysed through the project implementation we have identified different strategic lines for exploitation. They are organised based on a potential timing for achievement, as in the following figure.

Figure 2. Roadmap for exploitation

Short-term (0–3 years) strategic vision

In the short term, exploitation will prioritise the establishment of a robust data system, the development of an interoperable infrastructure prototype and the activation of high-value use cases. Efforts focused on defining a data management framework capable of generating novel datasets, through the integration of a variety of infrastructures, while safeguarding sensitive information, aligned with FAIR and open data principles under a dual-technology approach. In parallel, a European-standardised data handling and storage prototype will be designed to enable research and industrial uptake, embedding mechanisms for secure processing and selective deletion of sensitive data. Early scientific production and demonstrator studies will be promoted to showcase the analytical potential of fibre sensing, alongside the identification and engagement of key private stakeholders to foster collaboration around data access and sharing. Enabling these processes depends on ensuring continued operation and data storage of existing sites, which is catalogued on sustainability planning for each site.

Within this set of actions, key barriers include the technical and financial burden of maintaining high-quality data curation while ensuring security compliance. Data scrubbing processes risk removing valuable information, potentially undermining dataset robustness, while tensions may arise between openness and privacy requirements. Infrastructure prototyping may face challenges in standardisation and in implementing seamless sensitive-data deletion without compromising usability.

Medium-term (3–10 years) strategic vision

Medium-term exploitation will centre on consolidating governance structure, partnerships development and improve user engagement. A sustainable governance model will be developed to manage data and

infrastructure operations, including the definition of a formal legal status (integration into existing infrastructures) to strengthen funding access and institutional legitimacy. Strategic partnerships with the private sector will articulate mutual value propositions, while a structured community of practice will integrate researchers working with fibre sensing technologies and uptake of data resources for further research developments. Engagement activities - mainly through sustained participation in scientific events and exploring new collaboration horizons- will expand to map and attract new user communities.

Within this term, governance development may be slowed by conflicting stakeholder interests and complex negotiations around funding and intellectual property. Legal formalisation processes are often lengthy and administratively demanding (e.g. formal integration into existing infrastructures). Finally, identifying and effectively reaching new user communities will require significant time and resources, potentially delaying broad adoption.

Long-term (Over 10 years) strategic vision

Long-term exploitation will focus on strategic positioning, scientific excellence and enhancing societal impact. Strengthening the infrastructure’s role within the ESFRI landscape will create synergies with other European initiatives and reinforce long-term sustainability. Continued investment in research and innovation will ensure technological leadership, supporting advanced sensing capabilities and process improvements - this is of particular relevance within the new submarine cables strategic policy documents pointing towards the technological relevance of submarine cables-based research.

Achieving long-term alignment with ESFRI and EU priorities may be challenged by evolving policy agendas and funding landscapes. Furthermore, translating complex technical results into actionable policy guidance may prove difficult, particularly where political will, regulatory readiness or institutional incentives to adopt research outcomes remain limited.

5.1 Key Exploitable Results

This section presents the project Key Exploitable Results – which align with the actions towards achieving the short-term strategic vision for SUBMERSE.

There are five Key Exploitable Results (KERs) based on the project activities: DAS and SOP Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites, operational dataflow system, , innovative methods for analysis of marine environments and seismic events as well as training modules. Each KER presents the relevant Technology Readiness Level (TRL) tracking the maturity of the tools employed. This is followed by the identification of the target audience for each tool and a brief strategy for exploitation of the specific KER. The latter includes enablers and potential barriers to identify the actions needed for the successful implementation of the strategies.

5.1.1 DAS Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites

KER 1	DAS Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites
Owner	Consortium – mainly WP2 related partners
TRL	Mainly 7. It is a function of applications, including: earthquake monitoring: 7; earthquake early warning: 5; tsunami monitoring and early warning: 2; oceanography: 4; cetacean PAM: 4.

KER 1	DAS Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites
Target Audience	Research partners, cable operators, environmental monitoring agencies ; IRU owners & operators, network operators, subsea maintenance companies, Critical-infrastructure owners , Utilities & Energy, Coastal Authorities / environmental agencies, Defence/Security minded agencies, Insurance & risk managers, Data centres / hyperscalers , system vendors Operational Technology (OT) integrator, Procurement bodies / donors / EU projects, NREs, Early warning services, for earthquake and tsunami. Oceanographic observations of near shore SWH and surface currents. PAM of baleen whales.

Main strategies for exploitation: promote pilot results for wider adoption in cable industry; enable access to extended data sets for marine sensing; seek commercial partnerships and funded research; analysis of real time data for cable protection. Finally, the possibility to offer DAS-as-a-service solution.

Value propositions (different audiences):

- Operational: reduce mean-time-to-repair, targeted vessel dispatch, lower maintenance OPEX.
- Commercial: new monitoring service (DAS-as-a-service), premium SLA tiers.
- Scientific/regulatory: validated environmental monitoring datasets, compliance reporting.
- Risk & security: faster anomaly detection and forensic timelines.

Routes to market:

- Managed service (subscription for continuous monitoring)
- Data licensing: Sell event streams or historical datasets for commercial use (keeping non-commercial use free).
- Professional Services: consulting + integration + custom analytics
- White label: bundle DAS as part of telecom vendor / system integrator offerings
- Spin-out: commercialise core analytics or cloud ingestion stack with IRU owner.
- Grant / public good: for environmental/academic use, publish anonymised datasets, use grants to underwrite early operations.
- Offer monitoring & analytics to many different stakeholders interested in DAS data; publish selected datasets for research/public good.
- Make data available via well-developed data distribution services, at the national and international levels. These are missing for PAM.

Enablers: demonstrated data reliability; existing partnership network, including clear governance, contracts and funding; Strong research–industry partnerships; real time monitoring; existing IRU/cable access, demonstrable

PoC results, regulatory drivers which encourage monitoring (NIS2, 5G toolkit), API & integration readiness, strong tech stack;

Barriers: regulatory concerns; commercial constraints in IRU contracts; technical constraints; Data privacy concerns and Security concerns (e.g. scanning algorithm maturity, Liability and insurance for false or missing detections, Multi-jurisdiction complexity); funding for future deployments; existing contracts that will not allow any data sharing/transfer; costs (DAS maintenance costs and OPEX costs -Escort & hand and eyes cost); colocation access and power; skills shortage, Short(er) distance of sensing capability; data ownership and governance disputes (e.g. use of in-kind donated fibre); long procurement and vetting cycles with cable operators with submarine cable operators (especially those on repeated systems)

5.1.2 SOP Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites

KER 2	SOP Fiber sensing installed and configured in sites
Owner	Consortium – mainly WP2 related partners
TRL	Mainly 5-6
Target Audience	Research Community / Submarine cable operators; IRU owners & operators, network operators, subsea maintenance companies, Critical-infrastructure owners , Utilities & Energy, Coastal Authorities / environmental agencies, Defence/Security minded agencies, Insurance & risk managers, Data centres / hyperscalers , system vendors Operational Technology (OT) integrator, Procurement bodies / donors / EU projects, NRENs

Main strategies for exploitation: the primary exploitation strategy SOP submarine fibre sensing is to leverage existing transoceanic telecommunication cables as a distributed array of environmental and geophysical sensors. As for SOP normal data traffic can be used the SOP integration can be made with minimal hardware investment. SOP leverages This approach, often called "network as a sensor," emphasises the fact that external perturbations like seismic waves (earthquakes), ocean currents, sea swells, and changes in pressure or temperature induce small but measurable changes in the optical fibre's birefringence, which are reflected in the light's SOP. By simply monitoring the SOP (often already measured by standard coherent receivers for data demodulation using Digital Signal Processors (DSP), obtaining the sensing information "for free") at the end of the cable, researchers can detect these events over thousands of kilometres. Furthermore, more advanced techniques, like using high-loss loop-backs (HLLBs) present in many modern repeaters or launching polarisation-varying pulses, allow for localisation of these disturbances to specific repeater-to-repeater cable spans, dramatically improving the ability to monitor vast, otherwise unmonitored ocean floors for early warning systems and scientific research.

Additional strategies include: leverage results to develop new monitoring tools/services; explore licensing requirements or know-how; encourage further joint R&D and commercialisation with EllaLink and other stakeholders - SOP-as-a-service – managed services with continuous premium fibre monitoring; position SOP as low-cost complement to DAS; validate in pilots with Nokia/EllaLink for event detection.

Value propositions (different audiences):

- Operational: reduce mean-time-to-repair, targeted vessel dispatch, lower maintenance OPEX.

- Commercial: new monitoring service (Sensing-as-a-service), premium SLA tiers.
- Scientific/regulatory: validated environmental monitoring datasets, compliance reporting.
- Risk & security: faster anomaly detection and forensic timelines.

Routes to market:

- Managed service (subscription for continuous monitoring)
- Data licensing: Sell event streams or historical datasets for commercial use (keeping non-commercial use free).
- Professional Services: consulting + integration + custom analytics
- White label: bundle DAS as part of telecom vendor / system integrator offerings
- Spin-out: commercialise core analytics or cloud ingestion stack with IRU owner.
- Grant / public good: for environmental/academic use, publish anonymised datasets, use grants to underwrite early operations.

Enablers: Proven integration capabilities; industry reputation; academia interest; demonstrable PoC results; regulatory drivers which encourage monitoring (NIS2, 5G toolkit), strong tech stack, clear governance and contracts, Existing partnerships which strong research underpinning, funding and procurement pathways, Low capex and OPEX costs; long distance sensing capabilities. Further enablers include:

- Coherent optical transceivers: The most significant enabler. Modern long-haul fibre optic systems intrinsically measure the SOP (Stokes parameters/vectors of the incoming light for signal processing, making the sensing data available "embedded" with standard data transmission without needing to install new, dedicated sensors or dark fibre.
- Existing submarine cable infrastructure: The globally spanning network of telecommunication submarine cables acts as the sensor platform itself turning over one million kilometres of fibre into an extensive sensor array.
- Digital Signal Processing (DSP): Sophisticated DSP algorithms are essential for extracting SOP changes from the raw data stream. These algorithms are required to separate the SOP transitions caused by seismic activity, ocean currents, or temperature changes from the SOP fluctuations caused by the data traffic and the cable's internal components.
- Dedicated SOP hardware: In the situation the coherent optical transmission systems and the polarization modulation techniques (which are then processed in DSP) are not sufficient for fibre sensing use cases (usually due to their low sampling frequency around 100Hz), submarine link could be equipped with specialized SOP measuring devices like CESNET PoIBox or Novoptel PM1000.

Barriers: potential data ownership disputes; regulatory concerns; commercial constraints in IRU contracts; security concerns (security scanning algorithm maturity; liability and insurance for false or missing detections; multi-jurisdiction complexity); use of in-kind donated fibre (raising data ownership disputes); technical constraints – nascent technology which is not as accurate or detailed as DAS; Long procurement cycles; Long technology vetting cycle with submarine cable operators (especially those on repeated systems); Skills shortage; API integration readiness, maturity of tools and techniques to analyse the data; market fragmentation; need for

further validation; lack of resources/skills to analyse the high amount of data; need for robust detection algorithms and skills, regulatory drivers.

As additional barrier, SOP monitoring provides a cumulative measurement of environmental (external) vibrations integrated over the entire length of the monitored fibre span. Unlike Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), SOP generally cannot pinpoint the exact location of a disturbance, which limits its utility for maintenance, targeted inspection, or precise event analysis. Advanced techniques like using High-Loss Loop-Backs (HLLBs) offer some segmentation but don't achieve full distributed sensing.

The SOP is affected by both the external environmental events (the desired signal) and internal effects from the telecommunications system (the noise). This noise includes rapid, intentional SOP adjustments by the coherent receiver's Digital Signal Processor (DSP) to track and mitigate Polarization Mode Dispersion (PMD) for data recovery, as well as movements of patch cords in landing stations. Distinguishing the subtle, slow environmental shifts (e.g., from ocean currents or tides) from the fast, high-power communication-related fluctuations is a significant data processing challenge, often requiring complex filtering and advanced Machine Learning (ML).

5.1.3 Operational dataflow system

KER 3	Operational dataflow system
Owner	Consortium – mainly WP2 related partners
TRL	Mainly 7
Target Audience	Research community (PHD Students, Data scientists, marine researchers) and operational users (IPMA, civil protection, seismic, oceanographic, environmental agencies), Network operators, EU project, Early warning services, for earthquake and tsunami.

Main strategies for exploitation

Maintain and enhance the pipeline for real-time sensor data collection, processing and delivery; enable third-party research and monitoring; support scaling and new sensor integrations; anticipate announced institutions extinguishing in Portugal (FCT, FCCN); use NRENs as main transport for raw data; avoid storing raw data in field units and send it directly to secure national storage/analysis facilities; make data distributed using Seiscomp, seedlink and miniseed files via EIDA nodes

Value propositions (different audiences):

- Operational: lower maintenance OPEX.
- Commercial: new monitoring service (DAS-as-a-service), premium SLA tiers.
- Scientific/regulatory: validated environmental monitoring datasets, compliance reporting.
- Risk & security: faster anomaly detection and forensic timelines.

Enablers: Government-owned trusted entity hosting storage and analysis, with controlled access for researchers and operational users; existing infra (hosting) established data pipeline, cloud or on-prem infra; existing national

constructs; demonstrable PoC results; regulatory drivers which encourage monitoring (NIS2, 5G toolkit), API & integration readiness; strong tech stack; clear governance and contracts; existing partnerships which strong research underpinning; funding and procurement pathways

Barriers: Data access restrictions, integration with new sensors, maintenance costs, governmental changes and impact on institutions. Data ownership disputes; regulatory concerns; commercial constraints in IRU contracts; security concerns (Lack of government ownership/control may be seen as a national security risk, limiting both research and operational benefits); technical constraints; High OPEX costs for power, space, data storage, skills shortage or not core business for national stakeholders.

5.1.4 Innovative methods for analysis on ocean and seismic research

KER 4	Innovative methods for analysis on ocean and seismic research
Owner	Consortium – mainly WP3/4 related partners
TRL	Mainly 5-6
Target Audience	Research Community (the Seismology, Oceanography and Biology communities) Cable/DAS owners

Main strategies for exploitation: Creation and deployment of machine learning (ML) methods for real-time and accurate detection of specified events of interest from the perspective of marine researchers, e.g., whale sensing, storm detection. Data available in near real time using well established data distribution services. These are missing for PAM. Creation and deployment of machine learning (ML) methods for real-time and accurate detection of specified events of interest from the perspective of the seismographic research community, e.g., S-wave and P-wave segmentation, earthquake early warning detection system.

Value propositions (different audiences):

- Scientific/regulatory: validated environmental monitoring datasets, compliance reporting.
- Risk & security: faster anomaly detection and forensic timelines.

Routes to market

- Professional Services: consulting + integration + custom analytics
- White label: bundle tools as part of telecom vendor / system integrator offerings
- Spin-out: commercialise core analytics or cloud ingestion stack with consortium participants.
- Grant / public good: for environmental/academic use, publish anonymised datasets with tools, use grants to underwrite further adaptations and methods.

Enablers: demonstrable PoC results; regulatory drivers which encourage monitoring for security and protection purposes (NIS2, 5G toolkit); API & integration readiness; strong tech stack; existing partnerships which strong research underpinning; funding and procurement pathways; national and international data providers; working POC for vessel and earthquake detection from Svalbard’s cable

Barriers: IP ownership disputes; Skills shortages; lack of sufficient amount of labelled data from DAS that correspond to events of interest. No methods that could be trained in unsupervised manner allowing to create cable-agnostic methods.

5.1.5 Training modules

KER 5	Training modules
Owner	Consortium – mainly WP4 related partners / task leader
TRL	Mainly 5
Target Audience	Research institutions, industry partners, cable operators, network engineers, educational bodies, seismology community

Main strategies for exploitation: to train researchers in the field of environment, seismology, ecology, how to work with time series and data formats, such as HDF5, and also basic analyses of this data (e.g. using Python and relevant libraries), including ML techniques for reliable anomaly detection. Integrate modules into partner training programs, share with wider community via public repositories, offer as onboarding material for new staff and future EU projects; potential to expand into e-learning or certification programs in collaboration with Academy Consortium members (INESCTEC, FCUN). The strategy could also go through professional services: consulting + integration + custom analytics.

Enablers: Proper training environment, e.g. Jupyter Notebooks and a suitable e-Learning Platform; high-quality content developed; demand for upskilling in submarine systems; support from partners for dissemination; demonstrable PoC results; existing partnerships which strong research underpinning.

Barriers: Reliable reduction of the data to be worked with, so that noise is carefully removed; limited resources for ongoing updates; language accessibility; outreach effectiveness; limited number of training modules offered; skills shortage.

5.2 Partners Exploitation Profiles

This section outlines each partner’s interests in exploiting the project outcomes, their relevant expertise, resources and networks as well as their capacity to support further development, uptake and commercialisation where appropriate. At the same time, the section acknowledges any constraints that may influence exploitation activities, such as organisational mandates, market positioning or resource limitations. This overview provides a picture of how the consortium collectively and individually can contribute to maximising the long-term impact and sustainability of the project results.

Partner	EFIS
Interests for exploitation	Policy development in the field of research infrastructures and associated implications for coordinating and governance efforts. Further interest relies on the field of resilience of submarine cables and infrastructures in general. Key interests rely on the analysis of impact of the proposed infrastructures.
Capacity for exploitation	Long experience in RI field and socio-economic impact assessment for Ris in Europe. Staff capacity and skills.
Limitations for exploitation	Lack of specific funding to attend sectoral events discussing relevant policy developments, but possible synergy with other existing or future projects and innovation activities run by EFIS Centre and networks.

Partner	GÉANT Association
Interests for exploitation	Cross boarder data generation, DAS and SOP ownership, fibre ownership, data processing, facilitation of cross-disciplinary research, architecture adaptation to alternative fields such as security, monitoring of critical infrastructure.
Capacity for exploitation	OptoDAS interrogator (purchased outside of project), Preveza-Crotone cable landing station sensing sites to support additional sensor deployments, SOP transponder from Preveza-Crotone, European backbone telecoms network (including other submarine links), European gateway infrastructure (Bella, Blue Ramen, Medusa). Participating in the GN5-2 and GN5-3 projects which has a fibre sensing sub-task focused on developing fibre sensing awareness and potentially services for NRENS.
Limitations for exploitation	Preveza-Crotone has limited capacity for expansion (rack space and power), fibre that DAS units are deployed on in Preveza-Crotone is not owned by GÉANT and was an in-kind contribution for length of project, re-engineering of Preveza-Crotone link to support DAS on GÉANT owned fibre is not feasible at this stage, funding for on-going site operations doesn't include provision for sensing equipment (such as power) following end of the project. Operational focus of organisation is not fully aligned to incorporate sensing as core business. No specific funding allocation for sensing equipment, storage or processing of data for research communities following the end of the project.

Partner	GRENA
Interests for exploitation	GRENA has interest in fiber sensing infrastructure deployment at the Georgian research and education network. Planned usage fields are network monitoring and analyses of seismic events in cooperation with Institute for Earth Sciences.
Capacity for exploitation	GRENA owns fiber optic network that can be used for fiber sensing, also GRENA data center to analyse and store obtained data.
Limitations for exploitation	GRENA technical staff have no working experience with fiber sensing technology, also lack of financial resources available for this activity is clear limitation. Together with relevant research organizations we are discussing possibility to apply for dedicated funding from the government.

Partner	PCSS
Interests for exploitation	Development of machine learning framework for analysis of fibre optic sensing (FOS) data, including possibility to train and deploy both custom and pre-defined models for event detection or denoising.
Capacity for exploitation	Infrastructure for training future machine learning models.
Limitations for exploitation	No specific funding allowing for further development of novel machine learning methods for FOS (i.e., unsupervised methods for cable-agnostic models).

Partner	CESNET
Interests for exploitation	SOP data processing, Time Series Dimensional Reduction, Machine Learning models training, training with SOP datasets
Capacity for exploitation	One PolBox, Remote HDF5 storage, Jupyter Notebooks, lit fibre with DWDM data traffic, IP connectivity
Limitations for exploitation	Data security connected with SOP HDF5 timeseries, data labelling issues, no permanent or semi-permanent storage foreseen beyond the end of SUBMERSE

Partner	ELLA LINK
Interests for exploitation	Ella Link is going to use project learnings to strengthen shallow waters cable security, risk assessments, and incident preparedness. It will translate relevant outcomes into new customer services (e.g., improved SLA confidence, operational transparency at an appropriate level). Then, it will contribute to (and adopt) innovations and best practices/standards where feasible. Finally, it will leverage results to deepen collaboration with landing-station stakeholders, marine service providers, regulators, and the research community (with strict information governance).
Capacity for exploitation	In-house network operations, maintenance planning, supplier management, and incident coordination capabilities to operationalise applicable outputs. Know-how to incorporate new processes and features into products/services and customer commitments (e.g., operational processes, service reporting).
Limitations for exploitation	It consists in operational costs linked to exploitation activities must be covered by external funding (e.g. dedicated customer or programme budget). Strong restrictions on sharing operational details, network topology, security controls, vulnerabilities, landing-station specifics, or incident data that could elevate risk. Any exploitation action that changes processes, tooling, supplier interfaces, or publications requires formal security/risk review and approval; timelines may be impacted. Compliance obligations (including national/EU requirements) and customer/supplier confidentiality clauses may limit what can be reused or disclosed externally. Implementation windows constrained by commercial service priority, change management, maintenance cycles, and availability requirements; “do no harm” principle overrides speed of adoption.

Partner	DTU
Interests for exploitation	<p>The Danish Research Network is aiming to increase the use of fibre sensing in their cables. We have an ongoing collaboration with GEUS (Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland) where DAS interrogators owned by GEUS are used long-term on one cable and another one moving around for short term data collection.</p> <p>Apart from supporting Academia's application of fibre sensing data in many scientific areas, DeiC is interested in facilitating a collaborative approach including other stakeholders like Cable operators and security concerned agencies.</p>
Capacity for exploitation	<p>Since DeiC is the Danish NREN, the infrastructure in terms of access to cables, storage and compute facilities has been established. People within our organisation have acquired knowledge on different angles of fibre sensing (deployment, data management, data interpretation and security aspects). There is a need though, to further develop these in a collaborative approach considering the present geopolitical situation and recent EU legislation.</p>
Limitations for exploitation	<p>The biggest issue is the lack of funding since DAS interrogators are very expensive.</p> <p>Secondly, despite an ongoing dialogue with the Danish military and security services, there is always a risk of having a fibre sensing project shut down.</p> <p>Finally, if not handled properly, the recent EU directive NIS2 may lead to a more restrictive attitude towards giving Academia access to fiber sensing data.</p>

Partner	SIKT
Interests for exploitation	<p>Technology exploration and deployment. Storage and data processing environment, including secure operations.</p>
Capacity for exploitation	<p>Owns and control the national R&E network, very fit for transport of raw data in real time. Also own an entity provided secured HPC/storage facilities that fit the purpose</p>
Limitations for exploitation	<p>Initial funding for deployment and need to develop even strong partnership with both vetted researchers and government security agencies for continuous compliance.</p>

Partner	NOA
Interests for exploitation	<p>Data processing, use of DAS data in regional earthquake monitoring. Training</p>
Capacity for exploitation	<p>Operating the seismic network in Greece with experience in research, operation and data processing.</p>
Limitations for exploitation	<p>Inaccurate on non-access to full resolution data as no permanent or sea full resolution data as no permanent or semi-permanent storage foreseen beyond the end of SUBMERSE</p>

Partner	CORIAN / NOKIA
Interests for exploitation	Development of native network sensing integrated with telecom equipment or non-invasive optical solutions. Benchmarking technologies like ICE6 or ICE7 in submarine and terrestrial networks for enhanced monitoring, resilience, and disaster response. Advancing TRL of R&D efforts through collaboration with research partners and stakeholders. Enhancing Nokia's product portfolio and contributing to scientific research and supporting cable owners/operators.
Capacity for exploitation	Expertise in optical sensing and networking technologies and their integration into telecom equipment. Deployment and benchmarking of technologies in the same link as ICE6 and Polarimeter-based sensing. Containerized dataset building pipelines for repeatable deployment. Documentation of sensing technologies for collaboration and future exploitation. Strong global presence and established existing partnerships.
Limitations for exploitation	Still not standardised data formats and streams difficult the analysis for future technology iterations. Out-of-Europe colleagues not being eligible to access funds or work within the duration of the project limited the convenience of using all expertise within the company during the project and limit their ease at project result exploitation.

Partner	HCMR
Interests for exploitation	Data processing, data dissemination/distribution, cross-disciplinary research, training
Capacity for exploitation	HCMR/POSEIDON is an integrated observing and forecasting infrastructure for the Greek seas that collects and processes data from its own monitoring network and operates the Mediterranean node of the Copernicus Marine <i>in Situ</i> Thematic Assembly Centre, providing to CMEMS near-real time quality-controlled in-situ ocean observations.
Limitations for exploitation	Lack of in situ oceanographic observations during the DAS operating period limits the calibration/validation of the observed DAS- derived oceanographic signals.

Partner	UAH
Interests for exploitation	HW development and deployment experience.
Capacity for exploitation	UAH-CSIC research labs.
Limitations for exploitation	Public Entity. The technology is partially under exploitation

Partner	GFZ
Interests for exploitation	Data processing; use of DAS data for seismotectonic studies (building on analysis of offline data); use of data as test cases and benchmark for further development
Capacity for exploitation	Research environment at GFZ with several groups engaged with analysis of DAS data and improving DAS data management practices
Limitations for exploitation	Complex access rules impede, but hopefully will not stop, exploitation for scientific study. Although some in-house funded capacity is present, personnel capacity for further exploitation depends on success with third party projects. Data storage and access not secure for all sites.

Partner	CIENCIAS/FCID
Interests for exploitation	Main interest is on the DAS technology. Priority applications are earthquake monitoring, earth structure, early warning, physical oceanography, PAM of baleen whales.
Capacity for exploitation	Association with ARDITI, the owner and operator of the Madeira site DAS, developed routines for data processing and interpretation on the 3 domains, data storage via an association with IPMA
Limitations for exploitation	ARDITI has sustained funding for DAS acquisition, including manpower. CIENCIAS/FCID has funding project based, plus operation funding. One national project is ongoing, and a second project has been funded for 2 years by national funds.

Partner	INESC TEC
Interests for exploitation	Data processing, cross-disciplinary research, training
Capacity for exploitation	OptoDAS interrogator, Novoptel polarimeter, 1PB local storage, lab infrastructure for the simulation of 10Gb/s optical communication link spanning 100 km.
Limitations for exploitation	No specific funding allocated to INESC TEC storage, and no permanent or semi-permanent storage foreseen beyond the end of SUBMERSE.

Partner	LifeWatch ERIC
Interests for exploitation	Training, cross-disciplinary research, innovative methods for data analysis
Capacity for exploitation	Consolidated training infrastructure, Virtual Research Environments, active member in ENVRI Community and partner in biodiversity and environmental sciences research projects.
Limitations for exploitation	Training modules will require update and review by subject matter experts even after the project ends. Also, relevance of training content for scientific communities is strictly dependent on unrestricted access to continuous dataflow.

Partner	ASN
Interests for exploitation	HW deployment experience, requirements to data quality and real-time processing
Capacity for exploitation	OptoDAS R&D team, access to fibre-optic lab, customer field trials
Limitations for exploitation	Organisation strategy focus on HW development and pre-processing

Partner	UIB
Interests for exploitation	Data processing, use of DAS data in regional earthquake monitoring.
Capacity for exploitation	Operating the seismic network in Norway with experience in research, operation and data processing.
Limitations for exploitation	Access to data

Partner	RED CLARA
Interests for exploitation	Dissemination of project results, potential integration for use of data tools and SUBMERSE technology into LAC NREN infrastructure. A.o., promote the deployment of sensing-capable nodes on LAC cables, extend such infrastructure to Pan-American routes. Offer added value to LAC stakeholders (esp. researchers) through SUBMERSE data services and applications aligned with LAC priorities. Capacity building/knowledge transfer for LAC.
Capacity for exploitation	Connectivity infrastructure, with access to submarine cables. Outreach to interested LAC research communities.
Limitations for exploitation	Limited availability of funding and HR resources.

Partner	FCT & ARDITI
Interests for exploitation	Data processing, cross-disciplinary research, training
Capacity for exploitation	One OptoDAS interrogator, access to the GeoLab dark fibre, 1Gb private data link
Limitations for exploitation	No specific funding allocated to DAS, INESC TEC storage full (no new data uploaded since September 2025), no permanent or semi-permanent storage foreseen beyond the end of SUBMERSE

Appendix A SUBMERSE Impact Pathways

Figure 3. Overview of SUBMERSE activity-results-outcome-impact logics